

Good Practice Guide for EMC Emission Measurements with Direct Sampling Time Domain Measuring Receivers

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1 Scope

This document summarises some of the findings from the EMC-std project regarding Direct Sampling Time Domain Receivers when used in EMC applications. This includes information about the spectral estimation algorithms, calibration aspects with respect to EMC standardization and performance comparison with more traditional EMI-receivers in both calibration and realistic EMC measurements.

2 Introduction

For many years EMI measurement has been dominated by measurement receivers. Nowadays, alternatives have emerged, like spectrum analysers and FFT-receivers. Lately also oscilloscopes, together with specialized software (instrument internal or external) for spectral estimation and digital calculation of weighting detector responses like the quasi-peak detector, have entered the market for EMI evaluation purposes. Some features arise with this approach to EMI evaluation, like multi-channel measurements and triggering, smaller and cheaper instruments, reduced measurement time, more alternatives for time domain filtering and EMI spectrum visualization.

Up to now there have been some ambiguity on how to map these Direct Sampling Time Domain receivers against the requirements in instrument standardization for EMI measurements like the CISPR 16-1-1 [2].

This guide highlights the findings from the 21NRM06 EMC-std project where calibration results from different EMI receiver types have been compared against the results from Direct Sampling Receivers. It also shows some results from EMI measurements in realistic conducted emission setups together with a comparison of results between different receivers when exposed to controlled modulated signals.

As can be seen in coming sections and references, the results from Direct Sampling Time Domain Receivers are highly comparable to more traditional measurement receivers and spectrum analysers in the investigated calibration and measurement cases.

2.1 Abbreviations

EMC	Electromagnetic Compatibility
EMI	Electromagnetic Interference
Quasi-peak	Weighting detector for EMI-evaluation purposes defined in CISPR 16-1-1.
CISPR-Average	Weighting detector for EMI-evaluation purposes defined in CISPR 16-1-1.
CISPR-RMS	Weighting detector for EMI-evaluation purposes defined in CISPR 16-1-1.
VSWR	Voltage Standing Wave Ratio
PWM	Pulse Width Modulation
GaN	Gallium Nitride
RTSA	Real-Time Spectrum Analyzer

3 Spectral Estimation Parameters for Direct Sampling FFT-Based Measuring Receivers

The paper [1] investigates the accuracy of spectral estimation in EMI measuring receivers based on direct sampling and FFT processing. Since the CISPR 16-1-1[2] standard does not provide explicit guidance on spectral processing parameters, such as window functions, overlap, and interpolation, the study aims to evaluate the impact of these parameters on measurement accuracy. Three types of test signals were used: multitone, linear chirp, and rectangular pulses, covering the full frequency range of CISPR Bands A to D (9 kHz to 1 GHz).

Nearly 490,000 simulations were carried out using a MATLAB-based simulation platform that mimics a CISPR 16-1-1 compliant receiver. The tested parameters included 17 different window functions, overlap factors ranging from 50% to 95%, interpolation factors from 1 to 10, and four types of detectors (Peak, Average, Quasi-Peak, RMS). The error between the expected and estimated spectrum levels was computed for each configuration. Additionally, experimental validation was conducted using two oscilloscopes (R&S RTO64 and PicoScope 5444D), transformed into FFT-based measuring receivers via dedicated software.

The results show that Kaiser-Bessel and Parzen windows provide the most consistent and accurate results across all test signals, especially when combined with overlap factors of at least 75% and interpolation factors of 5 or higher. These settings minimized spectral estimation errors and ensured compliance with CISPR 16-1-1 requirements for tuning accuracy, pulse response, and selectivity. A qualitative comparison of all evaluated window functions is presented in Table 1, summarizing their performance across different signal types and CISPR bands.

The findings of this study are intended to support the configuration of time-domain EMI measurement receivers using FFT processing. The recommended parameter sets have already been implemented in the emiGO software and validated in an accredited calibration laboratory.

Windows	Selectivity			Accuracy									Result
	A	B	C/D	Multitone			Chirp			Rectpulse			
	A	B	C/D	A	B	C/D	A	B	C/D	A	B	C/D	
<i>Bartlett</i>	✓	✗	✓	✓✓	✗	✗	✓✓	✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✗	✗
<i>Mod Bartlett-Hanning</i>	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓✓	✗	✗	✗	✗
<i>Blackman</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓✓	✓✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗
<i>Blackman-Harris</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗
<i>Bohman</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✗	✗	✓✓	✗	✗	✗	✗
<i>Chebyshev</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓✓	✗	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✗	✓
<i>Flat-Top</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓✓	✗	✓✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗
<i>Gaussian</i>	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓✓	✓✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
<i>Hamming</i>	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓✓	✗	✗	✗	✗
<i>Hann</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓✓	✗	✗	✗	✗
<i>Kaiser-Bessel</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✗	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✗	✓✓
<i>Nuttall</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓	✓✓	✓	✓✓	✗	✓✓
<i>Parzen</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✗	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✗	✓✓
<i>Rectangular</i>	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓✓	✗	✗	✗
<i>Taylor</i>	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
<i>Tukey</i>	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
<i>Triangular</i>	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓	✗

Table 1 - Qualitative Summary of the Window Analysis Results.

4 Calibration aspects of EMC measurement receivers with time domain features

The calibration requirements for EMC measuring receivers are defined in the standard CISPR 16-1-1 [2] the latest version being from 2019. The standard defines standard detector types and frequency ranges. The detectors defined by the standard are “Quasi-peak”, “Peak”, “CISPR-Average” and “CISPR RMS-Average”. Each of the detectors is explained in detail in the standard. The frequency ranges are classified in several bands:

- Band A: 9 kHz to 150 kHz
- Band B: 150 kHz to 30 MHz
- Band C: 30 MHz to 300 MHz
- Band D: 300 MHz to 1000 MHz
- Band E: 1 GHz to 18 GHz

The calibration requirements and a criterion to demonstrate compliance with the standard are given in Annex K in the mentioned CISPR standard. The main requirements are input VSWR, sine-wave voltage tolerance, response to pulses and selectivity. In this chapter each of the requirements will be presented with a meta-analysis of some selected calibration points for different types of receivers.

More information regarding the calibration aspects can be found [3] .

4.1 Input VSWR

The standard in subclause 4.2 defines the limit for VSWR in the relevant frequency and input attenuation ranges. The limits can be seen in the following table. The nominal input impedance of the measuring receiver is 50 Ω .

Frequency range	Attenuation	VSWR
9 kHz to 1 GHz	0 dB	2,0 to 1
9 kHz to 1 GHz	≥ 10 dB	1,2 to 1
1 GHz to 18 GHz	0 dB	3,0 to 1
1 GHz to 18 GHz	≥ 10 dB	2,0 to 1

Table 2 - VSWR requirements for receiver input impedance; CISPR 16-1-1

The results of VSWR calibration for several different types of receivers can be seen in the following Figure 1. The results were collected from several participating calibration laboratories.

Figure 1 - Comparison VSWR measurements for different receivers

4.2 Sine-wave voltage tolerance

The standard in subclause 4.3 defines the limit that applies to the calibrated receiver with 50 Ω input impedance when measuring a sinewave. The limit is ± 2 dB up to 1 GHz and $\pm 2,5$ dB above 1 GHz.

The results for sine-wave tolerance measurement for different receivers are presented in Figure 2 and Figure 3. Measurements were made in CISPR frequency band A and B.

Figure 2 - Sine-wave voltage tolerance, Frequency band A.

Figure 3 - Sine-wave voltage tolerance, Frequency band B.

4.3 Response to pulses

The calibration requirements for pulse response are written in subclauses 5.2, 6.4, 7.3 and 8.3 in the standard for each detector type separately. In the case of quasi-peak detector, the calibration is divided into two parts. The absolute and relative calibration. Absolute calibration refers to receiver’s quasi-peak response to a defined pulse in terms of impulse area, central frequency and pulse repetition frequency. The standard’s definition can be seen in the following table. The standard’s defined limit is $\pm 1,5$ dB.

Frequency band	Impulse area	Frequency	Repetition rate
Band A	13,5 μ Vs	0,15 MHz	25 Hz
Band B	0,316 μ Vs	30 MHz	100 Hz
Band C	0,044 μ Vs	300 MHz	100 Hz
Band D	0,044 μ Vs	1000 MHz	100 Hz

Table 3 - Pulse definition, absolute calibration

The results of meta-analysis of obtained calibration data are presented in the following two figures for frequency bands A and B.

Figure 4 - Absolute calibration Band A

Figure 5 - Absolute calibration Band B.

4.4 Selectivity

Selectivity refers to the frequency pass-bandwidth of the selected CISPR resolution bandwidth filter. The filters are defined at 6 dB bandwidth with the pass-bandwidth:

- 200 Hz; Frequency band A
- 9 kHz; Frequency band B
- 120 kHz; Frequency band C/D
- 1 MHz; Frequency band E

The limits are defined in subclause 4.4 in figure form with exact limits at 1.5 dB, 6 dB and 20 dB. The results of meta-analysis of calibration data are presented in the same form in Figure 6 and Figure 7 for frequency band A and B.

Figure 6 - Selectivity band A

Figure 7 - Selectivity band B

5 Performance verification of Direct Sampling Time Domain Receivers by comparing results between different receiver types

The performance of the Direct Sampling Time Domain Receivers was validated by comparing the measurement results between several receivers in [REF1]. The used receivers can be seen in the table below.

	Manufacturer	Model	Software	Type
R1	Rhode & Schwarz	RTO64	emiGo	Direct sampling time domain receiver
R2	PicoScope	55444D	emiGo	Direct sampling time domain receiver
R3	Rhode & Schwarz	ESI 40	-	EMI Test receiver
R4	Rhode & Schwarz	ESW 8	-	EMI Test receiver
R8	Rhode & Schwarz	ESPI 7	-	EMI Test receiver
R9	Signal Hound	BB60C	-	Real time spectrum analyser

Table 4 - Receivers used in the performance verification.

5.1 Noise level comparison

A noise level comparison was performed for a subset of the receivers in Table 4 with the measurement port terminated in 50 Ohms, for parts of the CISRP frequency bands A-D. The peak detector results can be seen in figure, together with a MIL-STD-461G standard conducted emission limit as reference.

Figure 8 presents a comparison of the noise levels for receivers R1, R2, and R4 within the CISPR bands A–D. All three receivers exhibit sufficiently low noise floors. However, R4, when used in its intended configuration (i.e., without a preamplifier and with 10 dB of internal attenuation), shows a noticeably higher noise level compared to the others.

Additionally, Fig. 9 illustrates the noise floor measurements for receivers R2 and R8 within CISPR band A (9 kHz–150 kHz). All receivers maintain noise levels at least 30 dB μ V below the specified limit. The noise floor of R8 could be further reduced by lowering the attenuation level, although this would also narrow the measurable voltage range. To ensure consistency, the data shown in Figure 9 were obtained using the same configuration across all measurements.

Figure 8 - Noise level comparison for R1, R2, and R4 within CISPR bands A-D.

Figure 9 - Noise level comparison for R2, R8, and R9 within CISPR band A.

5.2 Performance validation with controlled modulation signals

In the controlled modulated signal comparison case, a signal/function generator was used to feed the receivers with signals under different modulation conditions in the CISPR frequency bands A to D. As seen in the result examples below, the results for the Direct Sampling Time Domain Receivers are comparable to the traditional measurement receivers for the used test cases. For more details see [Ref1].

Test signal	Parameters	CISPR Band	Receivers	Note
Pulsed RF	Pulse duration 20 μ s, repetition 1 ms	B-D	R1, R2, R3, R4	1, 2
Sinewave	1 V_{RMS} , 100 kHz	A	R2, R8, R9	3
Multitone	0.1 V_{RMS} each 20, 40, ..., 140 kHz	A	R2, R8, R9	3
Square signal	1 V_{PPK} , 20 kHz	A	R2, R8, R9	3
Chirp Signal	1 V_{RMS} , 80 kHz-120 kHz, t_{spr} 20 ms	A	R2, R8, R9	3
Spread Spectrum Square Signal	1 V_{PPK} , 18 kHz-22 kHz, t_{spr} 20 ms	A	R2, R8, R9	3

Note 1: More RF-pulse configurations are shown in [REF1].

Note 2: Receiver R2 has an upper frequency limit of 200 MHz, so no values for 500 MHz are shown for R2.

Note 3: Comparison are in reference to results from the traditional receiver R8.

Table 5 - Compared receivers, modulations and frequency bands.

For pulsed RF signals the results Figure 10 below was acquired. The measurements were repeated for several pulse durations and repetition times. The maximum deviation from the mean between all measured receivers for the Direct Sampling Time Domain Receivers was approximate 1.5 dB. This value was obtained for a centre frequency of 500 MHz, pulse duration of 50 μ s and a pulse repetition time of 1ms. For the traditional receivers the deviation was approximately 1.2 dB for the same pulse settings.

Figure 10 - Results for receiver performance verification with pulse modulated RF-signals.

Other modulations were also investigated for the CISPR frequency band A. The results can be seen in Table 6 below, as a deviation from the results of the traditional Test Receiver R8.

For the R9 receiver only peak values are shown, since this instrument has no implementation of the CISPR weighting detectors. Figures ___ - ___ demonstrate some results of the measurements with the probability density function (PDF) of the emissions in the 18–22 kHz band. For more details see [Ref1].

Modulation	Detector	R2 [dB]	R9 [dB]
Sinewave signal	Peak	0.08	0.08
	Average	0.08	-
	Quasipeak	0.34	-
Multitone signal	Peak	0.09	0.09
	Average	0.10	-
	Quasipeak	0.37	-
Square signal	Peak	0.26	4.39
	Average	1.00	-
	Quasipeak	2.02	-
Chirp Signal	Peak	0.01	0.14
	Average	0.85	-
	Quasipeak	0.01	-
Spread Spectrum square signal	Peak	0.08	0.19
	Average	0.59	-
	Quasipeak	0.12	-

Table 6 - Comparison results for controlled modulated signals in CISPR band A.

Figure 11: Results for receiver performance verification with modulated a) multitone and b) square signals.

Figure 12 - Receiver performance verification with modulated chirp signal: a) results, and b) PDF.

Figure 13 - Receiver performance verification with modulated spread spectrum square signal: a) results, and b) PDF.

For signals with stable frequency content, such as a square wave, R2 and R9 closely match the reference R8 in most cases, with deviations typically under 0.5 dB. However, when the signal amplitude is near the receiver's noise floor (e.g., at 120 kHz), the deviations increased, reaching up to 4.5 dB in average and quasi-peak detection modes. For signals with time-variant frequency content (e.g., chirp and spread-spectrum-modulated square waves), data were resampled for consistent comparison. R2 again showed strong agreement with R8, with average deviations below 1 dB and minimal differences in mode values. R9 exhibited slightly higher deviations, though still within acceptable limits. Overall, the R2 receiver consistently demonstrated high accuracy across various test signals, making it a reliable alternative to the reference receiver in both stable and dynamic EMI measurement scenarios.

5.3 Performance validation in realistic EMC test cases

Another part of [Ref1] shows receiver performance comparisons for realistic conducted emission test cases, with setups that resembles ordinary compliance testing setups. Conducted emissions were measured from two different DC/DC converters, a COST Buck/Boost converter (set up in Figure 14) and a PWM output modulated GaN. The latter was measured in three different operational modes.

The setup with COST DC/DC buck-boost converter was used to validate the measurements via R1 and R2 in comparison to R4. The focus was on evaluating harmonic and broadband voltage levels and identifying resonance effects by the measurement systems. Spectral data (Figure 15) were analysed, and comparisons were made across different frequency ranges and interpolation methods used by the receivers. More detailed information can be found in [Ref1].

Figure 14 - EMC Conducted emission setup for the Buck/Boost converter.

Figure 15 - Peak detector results from the Buck/Boost converter.

The conducted emissions of a CoolGaN™ 600 V half-bridge evaluation board were measured using the setup presented in Figure 16. This GaN converter is controlled by the development board. Three types of switching frequency modulation shown in Table 7. Two of them have been used to spread the spectrum of the emissions.

Figure 16 - The schematic of the measurement setup. The INM is measured via R2, R8 and R9 receivers.

PWM Type	Parameters
Continuous	20 kHz, Steady
Linear Spread Spectrum	18 kHz - 22 kHz, Period variation of 20 ms.
Random Spread Spectrum	18 kHz - 22 kHz, Period variation of 20 ms.

Table 7 - Characteristics of pulse width modulation for controlling a GaN converter.

The conducted emissions were measured in terms of normal mode current I_{NM} using an RF current probe. Measurement results under different PWM control strategies can be seen in Table 8. Figure 17 to Figure 19 demonstrate some results of the measurements. More detailed information can be found in [Ref1].

Converter mode	Detector	R2 [dB]	R9 [dB]
Continuous PWM	Peak	0.49	2.96
	Average	0.50	-
	Quasipeak	0.77	-
Linear SS PWM	Peak	1.09	1.21
	Average	1.09	-
	Quasipeak	1.63	-
Random SS PWM	Peak	1.40	2.63
	Average	0.54	-
	Quasipeak	2.44	-

Table 8 - Results from GaN converter compared to the R8 receiver.

For continuous PWM (20 kHz fundamental), the emissions resembled a square wave spectrum with distinct harmonic peaks below 150 kHz. The results from three receivers (R2, R8, and R9) were compared using peak, average, and quasi-peak detectors. R2 showed consistent agreement with the reference R8, with deviations below 0.8 dB. R9, however, showed higher deviations up to 2.96 dB at the fundamental frequency. Figure 17 shows the results for the peak detector.

Figure 17 - Peak detector results from GaN converter in **continuous** PWM mode.

Figure 18 - Peak detector results from GaN converter in **linear spread spectrum PWM** mode, (a) shows emission results and (b) shows PDF's.

Figure 19 - Peak detector results from GaN converter in **random spread spectrum PWM** mode, (a) shows emission results and (b) shows PDF's.

When using random spread spectrum PWM, the EMI spectrum became more complex and densely populated with peaks and dips across the frequency range. Despite this complexity, the PDF of the emissions in the 18–22kHz band indicated a high level of agreement between the receivers. On average, the deviation of R2 from the reference R8 remained within 2–3 dB for all detectors, with standard deviations up to 1.17 dB. Receiver R9 again exhibited slightly higher deviations compared to R2. Overall, the results validate that EMI from both PWM techniques can be reliably captured using the described measurement setup, with R2 providing the closest match to the reference system.

6 Conclusions

A methodology for measuring electromagnetic interference using direct-sampling receivers and FFT-based spectral processing was developed, simulated, and experimentally validated. Extensive numerical simulations were performed to evaluate different spectral estimation parameters, including window functions, overlap factors, and interpolation rates, for three types of test signals (multitone, linear chirp, and rectangular pulses) across the CISPR frequency range from 9 kHz to 1 GHz. More than 490,000 simulations demonstrated that Kaiser-Bessel and Parzen windows, combined with overlap $\geq 75\%$ and interpolation ≥ 5 , consistently yielded the lowest estimation errors. These findings were summarized into practical recommendations for FFT processing configurations suitable for time-domain measurement receivers.

In the next stage, practical measurements were carried out using oscilloscope-based instruments (R1 and R2) functioning as FFT receivers, and their results were compared to commercial

CISPR 16-1-1 compliant receivers (R8 and R9). Five stepwise experiments, ranging from simple to complex excitation signals, including spread-spectrum PWM, confirmed that R1 and R2 achieved amplitude and frequency accuracy within standard tolerances. Deviations across various detectors (PK, AVE, QP) remained within acceptable limits, confirming the reliability and consistency of the proposed time-domain measurement approach.

7 References

- [1] M. García-Bermúdez, J. Solé-Lloveras, M. Hudlička and M. A. Azpúrua, "Evaluation of Spectral Estimation Parameters for Direct Sampling FFT-Based Measuring Receivers," in *IEEE Open Journal of Signal Processing*, vol. 5, pp. 588-598, 2024, doi: 10.1109/OJSP.2024.3389825.
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